

RORESPONSE PAPER

LAST NAME: ALABI
FIRST NAME: BABATUNDE
PROGRAM CODE: DSDD
COURSE CODE: ACA-401D
PERIOD NUMBER: 1
INSTRUCTOR: DR. GULMA

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics

The author did use Turabian (in-text/parenthetical)

The student must use Turabian/Chicago parenthetical/in-text references (ideally with Zotero) and confirm below:

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author did use Grammarly Premium (provided by EUCLID)

My plagiarism rate (per Grammarly Premium) is: 1%

The author used the following software: MS Word 2016 on Windows 11

List your 5-7 key concepts with page number in text (then bold these terms in your RP)(samples below):

1. Writing an essay (EUCLID 2024, 7-12)
2. Appropriate use of punctuation (EUCLID 2024, 15-23)
3. American Vs. British English (EUCLID 2024, 24-32)
4. Plagiarism (EUCLID 2024, 33-39)
5. Style guide (EUCLID 2024, 40-42)
6. Sample paper review (EUCLID 2024, 61-64)

BEST PRACTICES FOR ACADEMIC ESSAY WRITING

1) INTRODUCTION

The ACA-401 Period 1 course is a learning guide for academic writing. The eight chapters in the material cover the essentials of writing academic papers, including the structuring of essays, the use of proper punctuation, variants of the English language, and considerations for ethics in academic writing. It also provides insights into how style guides can help achieve consistency in writing. Furthermore, the material reviews a sample paper to explain how students can apply the knowledge practically. Complementing this is a set of short video lectures that teach important Microsoft Word features, such as the style and the review functions, which offer technical support for preparing academic papers.

The course begins by providing an overview of essay writing, emphasizing clarity, coherence, and conformity to academic writing standards. The punctuation and American and British English chapters further help me understand the course concepts. The material also offers extensive discussions of the practice of ethical writing, particularly avoiding

plagiarism, along with guidelines for citations and referencing. The material concludes with practical examples, which help solidify the knowledge through reviewing a sample response paper.

This paper will explore six core concepts from all the study materials and put them within the context of my personal experiences as a student and professional.

2) WRITING AN ESSAY

Authors must adopt a structured approach that defines the question and creates a clear plan to write an academic paper that passes the test of quality (EUCLID 2024, 7). I cannot overstate the importance of this topic to me, given its emphasis on starting early and planning adequately, as delays and poor planning often negatively impact the quality of writing. For instance, I have found myself racing through important assignments a few times in my academic journey because of delays in commencement. This often produces poorly structured papers ridden with weak arguments. This experience lends credence to the value of time management and the stepwise method described in this course material.

A critical lesson from this course is writing an essay plan, systematically organizing ideas, and using paragraphs as “building blocks” for constructing arguments (EUCLID 2024, 10). I fully support this approach as it is consistent with my usual practice of breaking down ideas into clear sections and ensuring a logical flow. I work in a sector where I write much, and this approach has worked for me consistently. I have found this to help organize and clarify my thoughts, making me feel fulfilled in my writing.

3) APPROPRIATE USE OF PUNCTUATION

Punctuation ensures the clarity and precision of academic writing and helps to convey the intended meaning to its readers. The guidance provided by the course material on quotation marks, commas, and apostrophes remains very informative. Appropriate use of punctuation is something that I have struggled with both in my education and career. As much as I try to pay attention to this aspect of writing, I always need to correct a few punctuation errors. For instance, EUCLID (2024, 17) advises writers not to use apostrophes for plurals, a common mistake I make in my writing. I have consciously revisited these rules while writing, particularly in technical reports. With this consciousness, I have observed an improvement in the clarity of communication, especially when writing reports for diverse audiences.

The discussion on the Oxford comma was an instructive moment for me. The course content has improved my understanding of its use. Including it in a list prevents ambiguity, as illustrated in the example: “I ate fish, bread, and ice cream” (EUCLID 2024, 22). Before now, I had always thought it was acceptable to use the Oxford comma in all cases as long as it is consistent throughout the writing. However, it is enlightening to learn that its use should be limited to preventing ambiguity.

4) AMERICAN VS. BRITISH ENGLISH

This part of the study material is the most interesting for me. I am a student who hails from a former British colony where English is the spoken official language but whose culture is now heavily influenced by the culture and languages of the United States. With this multiculturalism, I have experienced endless confusion in how I and other people speak, pronounce, and write English. It is expected that British and American spellings and linguistic approaches will co-exist in the same writing authored by people from my country.

For example, EUCLID (2024, 27) highlights differences like “honour” (UK) versus “honor” (US), which often confuse non-native speakers. An example of the implication of language variants is when I worked on a collaborative project where inconsistencies in English variants between team members led to editing delays. The difference in spelling, pronunciation, and use of punctuation prolonged the review and editing process and consequently caused a delay in the project timeline. Adopting one of these two English variants aligned with EUCLID’s advice would help resolve such conflicts (Cleenewerck 2016).

5) PLAGIARISM

Plagiarism is an academic fraud that must be avoided at all costs, as this is the fulcrum of academic integrity. EUCLID (2024, 34) states, “Plagiarism is when the writer uses a source of information without giving credit to the author of that source of information.” In the early days of my writing, receiving feedback from professors about inadequate citations was common. However, things are different these days. I now check and recheck to ensure I give credit to whom it is due appropriately to avoid unintentional plagiarism. One quote from EUCLID (2024, 36) that readily comes to mind is, “Limit the use of quotations. If you use it too much, it does not look like your own research.” This suggestion is crucial as it reminded me to focus on synthesizing ideas rather than over-relying on direct quotes.

However, I am still trying to understand the need for diverse academic citation and reference styles. As a writer, I have had to learn different referencing styles, given that every school, journal, and institution has its preferred style. I have yet to come to terms with the need for diverse writing and citation styles in today’s interconnected world. I do not see any reason for it, and I look forward to a day when we will harmonize all the styles so that writers do not have to keep learning new styles every time. Despite this, I acknowledge the great relief that Zotero has brought into writing, helping to manage citations, references, and bibliographies in a way that reduces students’ burden and ensures academic writing standards are maintained.

6) STYLE GUIDE

The topic of the style guide is quite refreshing. I align with the study material's stand on consistency of writing style, as this is key to achieving quality in writing. EUCLID (2024, 41) notes, "A style guide provides a means of documenting basic rules or features of your writing that will allow you to ensure consistency in your written output." Maintaining consistency is a practice that I am particularly striving towards to enhance the credibility of my work. In many previous works, I have applied many writing styles depending on situational preferences. Among these, I find the American Psychological Association (APA) and Chicago styles particularly helpful in writing research reports and preparing manuscripts for publication. Both are relatively easy to use, perhaps because I have used them more than any other style, being the preferred styles in the jurisdictions where I have schooled and worked.

However, before now, I knew very little about the Turabian style and never knew it was a variant of the Chicago style. From a distance, I had always thought it was another type of style entirely. Now that I am beginning to interact with it more, I have realized that it is a much simpler version of the Chicago style, and I see it as very appropriate for students. My previous interactions with too many writing styles may challenge my writing, especially in maintaining consistency. This consideration is critical because many style elements include layout, font, spelling, abbreviations, and many more (EUCLID 2024, 41). I must pay more attention to ensure consistency in my writing across all these aspects.

7) SAMPLE PAPER REVIEW

The sample response paper reviewed in the study material provided practical insights into what constitutes quality writing. EUCLID (2024, 63) highlights the importance of analyzing structure and logical flow. The reviewer flagged several writing inconsistencies in the paper, including inappropriate use of abbreviations and punctuations, particularly commas, unnecessary use of adverbs, random capitalization, and inappropriate citations. In the video sample tutorial, the reviewer draws students' attention to other writing issues, including contractions, periods before citations, and improper citing of web pages (Gulma 2022). There are many more inconsistencies and inaccuracies present in the sample paper that the reviewer did not flag. For example, "over whelming" instead of "overwhelming," writing "am" instead of "I am," "critic" instead of "critique," and many more.

Reviewing student writing before assigning grades is suitable because it helps students learn better and apply corrections in their current and future writing. During my graduate studies, I had a professor who instituted two levels of review for my class. The first was peer review, which helped refine my draft papers. These review sessions also enabled me to critique other students' work, helped me learn more from my classmates, provided helpful feedback, and received valuable insight into my writing, resulting in improved grades. The second level of review was that by the professor himself. He would review, provide feedback to students, and ask for revision and resubmission. While this

approach felt cumbersome for me and other students, we found it very helpful as it significantly improved my writing and grades.

8) CONCLUSION

The ACA-401 course material has drawn my attention to many things I often overlook and has reshaped how I think of my academic writing approach. I have found this course very helpful in highlighting how integrating essential skills like proper punctuation, ethical standards, and adherence to the style guide can help students succeed academically. The video lessons also offer practical learning that complements the primary material and provides specific directions for achieving academic excellence. In this response paper, I have reflected on and situated my opinions and thoughts within the context of my personal experiences. These experiences align primarily with EUCLID's teaching philosophy.

REFERENCES

Cleenewerck, Laurent, dir. 2016. *Understanding Templates and Styles for ACA-401*. Vimeo.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Gulma. 2024. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. Fifth Edition. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.

Gulma, Kabiru, dir. 2022. *Sample RP Review Video*. YouTube.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.